

Towards Reproducible and Interactive Research: Live Code Execution for Data-Driven Insights

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Abstract

Ensuring the proper management of *Research Digital Objects* (RDOs)—such as datasets, publications, and software—following the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) [1] has become a cornerstone of good scientific practice. Appropriate research data management (RDM) is essential to foster discovery, transparency, and reproducibility. However, despite advancements in RDM infrastructures, many platforms lack integrated environments for dynamic exploration, analysis, and visualization of data. Traditional approaches often require researchers to download datasets, configure local environments, and manage dependencies manually, which hinders collaboration, increases the risk of reproducibility errors, and creates high entry barriers for non-technical users. These limitations restrict the full exploitation of research data in academic and educational settings [2].

To address these challenges, we introduce a live code execution framework integrated into the *Leibniz Data Manager* (LDM) [3], a platform combining research data management with knowledge graphs and neuro-symbolic AI [4]. Our framework enables users to execute, modify, and experiment with code directly within LDM, removing the need for local installations. By leveraging JupyterHub¹ and DockerSpawner², we provide isolated, secure, and reproducible environments based on Docker containers. Each user receives a personalized session with full write access, allowing actions such as cloning Git repositories, installing additional packages, and persisting files temporarily during the session, while ensuring environmental integrity and security. Furthermore, we automate the conversion of R and Python scripts into interactive Jupyter notebooks. These notebook versions maintain dynamic links to the original scripts, ensuring that updates are reflected in real time and that obsolete notebooks are automatically cleaned up when source files are removed.

Scalability and operational control are ensured through an integrated admin panel that allows administrators to configure key aspects of the live code framework. This includes setting session timeouts, managing the maximum number of concurrent users,

¹<https://jupyter.org/hub>

²<https://jupyterhub-dockerspawner.readthedocs.io>

and defining resource constraints such as CPU allocation (as a percentage of a core), memory limits, and container storage sizes. These settings enable the LDM platform to balance performance, user experience, and infrastructure costs while ensuring usability and computational security across the system. The automatic session reset mechanism ensures that any changes made during a session are reverted after a timeout, providing a consistent and clean environment for every user interaction. This allows researchers and students to explore, visualize, and analyze data in real time while preserving computational integrity.

The proposed framework directly benefits researchers, educators, and infrastructure providers. For researchers, it offers an immediate, interactive environment to explore and analyze data without technical barriers, improving the reproducibility and transparency of scientific workflows. For educators and students, it serves as a powerful teaching tool, enabling active engagement with real-world data and computational experiments in a controlled, low-threshold setting. Infrastructure providers benefit from operational scalability and resource control without compromising user flexibility. By bridging the gap between static RDM and interactive computing, our solution strengthens the usability and accessibility of research data platforms and supports the broader goals of open science and reproducible research.

Resources

The following resources support and are closely related to our contribution:

- Leibniz Data Manager (LDM): https://github.com/SDM-TIB/LDM_Docker. Docker-based deployment environment including services for RDM, knowledge graphs, federated search, datasets comparison, and live code execution.
- ckanext-jupyternotebook: <https://github.com/SDM-TIB/ckanext-jupyternotebook>. A CKAN extension that integrates live, interactive Jupyter notebook environments into data portals.
- ckanext-Code2NB: <https://github.com/SDM-TIB/ckanext-Code2NB>. A plugin that automatically converts R and Python scripts into interactive Jupyter notebooks within CKAN.

Author contributions

Ariam Rivas: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing

Philipp D. Rohde: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing

Maria-Esther Vidal: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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